

Evolution of the lightning zoning guideline and coming challenges for lightning protections of unconventional platforms

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Keywords: lightning, zoning, modelling, helicopter, VTOL.

1. ABSTRACT

The lightning zoning is a cornerstone in the upstream lightning hazards analysis, in the purpose to define the threat at rotorcraft and at system levels, for both lightning direct and indirect effects.

From 2014 to 2018, the regulatory working groups SAE-AE-2 and EUROCAE WG31 have reviewed the lightning zoning document. A new issue was released (ED-91A or ARP5414B), as the result of the analysis of in-service experience (location and type of damage and failures), and leading to a better adaptation of the standard to the reality for the various types of aircraft including rotorcraft. This zoning of rotorcraft was a common work between five Helicopters manufacturers based on an initial proposal of Airbus.

The main modification consists in the suppression of the lightning zone 2 (high probability of sweeping strike) of the airframe and of the zone 1 (high probability of attachment) on the nose. As the airframe is mainly in zone 3 (low probability of attachment), there is a need to consider the local effect of the protrusions (antennas, FLIR cameras...) on the zoning, and the possible creation of local zones 3 direct attachment (peak up to 40KA) or zone 1 (peak up to 200 KA).

That work shows consequently the need to have a prediction tool to support the assessment of the local threat and in particular to evaluate the effect of protrusions on the attachment risk. It is mentioned in ED-91A/ARP5414B that there is a need for validation. Such an activity is obviously essential for new shapes as VTOL with multi-rotor configurations for which experience is rather absent.

Existing electromagnetic tools can be used, but still need validation for a better prediction. The final goal would be to have a validated means of compliance or at least as an intermediate step a help for the design of protections and the certification phases.

The first part of the paper provides an overview in terms of in service experience and zoning tools based on Airbus experience. The second part reports the results obtained on a complete Helicopter with the Airbus electromagnetic numerical tool for primary attachment locations prediction, the limitations of such a prediction tool and the recommendations in terms of utilization of the tool and associated protection policy.

2. ACRONYMS

Table 1: Acronyms

AC	Advisory Circular
AH	Airbus Helicopter
CFRP	Carbon Fiber Reinforced Polymers
FLG	Front Landing Gear
FLIR	Forward Looking Infra-Red
H/C	Helicopter
LIE	Lightning Indirect Effects
LDE	Lightning Direct Effects
MLG	Main Landing Gear
VTOL	Vertical Take-off and Landing
WG	Working Group

3. LIGHTNING THREAT & LIGHTNING ZONING

3.1 Lightning Requirements

The airworthiness requirements related to LDE are provided in § 610 and § 954 of the parts CS29/CS27 [1] and guidance material is given in AC-29-2C/AC-27-1 [2]. The airworthiness requirements for LIE are provided in § 1309 of CS27/29 respectively CS27/29 and guidance material is given in AC/AMC 20.136A [3] and ARP 5415/ED158 [4]. On a general point of view, for both civilian and military rotorcraft, the requirement may be summarized as follows: “*After a lightning strike, the H/C will be capable of a safe return flight and landing*”. For instance, the basic duration of the return flight to consider may be the half autonomy.

3.2 Evolution of the Regulation

To define the global threat on an aircraft, the lightning zoning provided in documents EUROCAE WG31 ED-91 / SAE-AE-2 ARP5414 [6] are used. For rotorcraft, the ED-91/ARP5414A provides the following zoning:

FORWARD and HOVER FLIGHTS
Figure 1: Previous lightning zoning

With the following definitions:

- Zone 1A and 1B : area of the aircraft surfaces where a first return stroke is likely during lightning attachment, with respectively a low and a high expectation of flash hang on,
- Zone 1C : area of the aircraft surfaces where a first return stroke of reduced amplitude is likely during lightning attachment, with a low expectation of flash hang on,
- Zone 2A and 2B: area of the aircraft surfaces where subsequent return stroke is likely to be swept with respectively a low and a high expectation of flash hang on,
- Zone 3: areas other than those covered by Zone 1 (attachment) and Zone 2 (re-attachment or sweeping) regions. In Zone 3, any attachment of the lightning channel is unlikely. Aircraft portions in zone 3 area lie beneath or between the other zones (1A, 1B, 1C, 2A and 2B) and/or conduct substantial amounts of electrical current between direct or swept stroke attachment points.
- Zone 3N (direct attachment): reserved for new or novel designs, without experience, and susceptible to endanger safety.

The standard (see ARP 5412A/ED84A [5], “Aircraft Lightning Environment and Related Test Waveforms”) also defines the component characteristics of the current in a natural lightning flash, and the levels of severity to apply to each risk zone for the lightning current tests.

Figure 2: Current components waveforms

With:

Component A (Initial Strike)

Peak amplitude = 200 kA +/- 10%

Action integral = $2 \times 10^6 A^2 \cdot S$ +/- 20%

Time duration = 500 μs

Component B (Intermediate Current)

Maximum charge transfer = 10 Coulombs

Average Amplitude = 2KA +/- 10%

Component C (Continuing Current)

Charge transfer = 200 Coulombs +/- 20%

Amplitude = 200 - 800A

Component D (Re-strike)

Peak amplitude = 100 kA +/- 10%

Action integral = $0.25 \times 10^6 A^2 \cdot S$ +/- 20%

Time duration = 500 μs

Component Ah

Peak amplitude = 150 kA +/- 10%

Action integral = $0.8 \times 10^6 A^2 \cdot S$ +/- 20%

Time duration = 500 μs

Tableau 2: Current components waveforms versus the zoning for lightning test (direct structural effects)

TEST	ZONE	WAVEFORMS CURRENT COMPONENT				
		A	B	C	D	Ah
DIRECT STRUCTURAL EFFECTS	1A	x	x	x(1)		
	1B	x	x	x	x	
	1C		x	x(1)	x	x
	2A		x	x(1)	x	
	2B		x	x	x	
	3 (conducted)	x	x	x	x	
	3 (Direct attachment for new or novel design)	A/5	x	x(1)		

(1): This component (modified component C) represents the portion of component C which flows into an attachment point in zone 1A or 2A if the dwell time at that point exceeds 5ms. This component is a current averaging not less than 400A for a period equal to the dwell time minus the 5ms duration of component B.

From 2014 to 2018, the regulatory working groups SAE-AE-2 and EUROCAE WG31 have reviewed the lightning zoning document. Concerning the rotorcraft, this new zoning, with an initial proposal of Airbus was discussed by five helicopter manufacturers (Bell, Robinson H/C, Sikorsky, Leonardo & Airbus) and is mainly based on in-flight experience (see next paragraph).

The main modifications are the suppression of lightning zones 2 (sweeping zone) of the airframe and of zones 1 on the nose.

Figure 3: New H/C Zoning

The airframe will be consequently mainly in zone 3 where any primary attachment or sweeping of the lightning channel is considered unlikely, but emphasizes the role of the protrusions which may modify locally the zoning with possibly risk of attachment.

“Small protrusions” as defined in ARP5414B/ED-91A are not impacting the lightning zoning. When the criterion to assimilate a protrusion to a “small protrusion” is not fulfilled, a zone 3N from the ARP5414A/ED-91 with a direct attachment to be considered at a reduced level (A/5 or 40 KA) could be a good compromise.

It should be noted that the zone 3N in ARP5414B/ED-91A is more dedicated to transport aircraft and in particular for the fuel areas in the wings, while in ARP5414A/ED-91 the meaning was more general and dedicated to novel shapes where experience is absent and risk of attachment can be suspected. Anyway, ARP5412A/ED-84A about lightning

environment associates 3N with novel shapes.

Also, for negative strikes, even if 40 KA seems a low level, the lightning statistics show that this level covers 70 to 80 % of the first return strokes, while 50% of strikes are around 20 KA, and the standardized 200 KA covers 95 to 99% of the cases ([7] containing Cianos & Pierce statistics). So, 40 KA covers a majority of strikes while staying in the general zone 3.

3.3 Airbus Helicopters Experience in Service

3.3.1 Strike Occurrence – General Data

According to document SAE-ARP-5412, the probability of a lightning strike to an aircraft depends on various parameters, e.g. the local climate, flight profile, type of aircraft.

From a significant sample of reported strikes to large transport aircraft operating in scheduled airline service, the average probability of a lightning strike has been estimated to be approximately one strike in every 10 000 flight hours. However, a separate study of transport aircraft experience within a region known to be prone to lightning estimated the average probability of a lightning strike to be approximately one strike in every 1000 flight hours.

These data are based on reported strikes, which get noticed because of bright light (especially at night), loud noises, associated physical damage effects, interference or damage to cockpit avionics. Other strikes to aircraft undoubtedly occur but go unnoticed or are not reported.

In the frame of a Certification, it should be noted that the risk is to be considered with a probability equal to 1 (the statistical data are not used for certification purposes).

3.3.2 Airbus H/Cs Experience

Data about in service incidents due to lightning strikes are collected from customer's supports, so that a continuous follow-up of in-flight incidents is performed and data are compiled in a specific database containing:

- General data of the incidents (H/C Number, meteorological data, location of the lightning strike, particular events noticed by the crew),
- Information about the damage obtained (including equipment failures).

Also, photos and other documents (inspections report ...) are collected in a specific resource.

Figure 4: AS350 (A-Star)

Figure 5: Main blade: Low damage when CFRP metallized

This follow-up and this database allow to ensure the continuous airworthiness and to update substantiation methods and protections if necessary (behavior of items and the adequacy of lightning zoning with sufficient protection, but also arguments to prevent excessive increase of severity in the regulations).

Part of this information is delivered in the present document (see the following two tables):

According to these data, 126 AH manufactured H/Cs were found struck from 1976 to 2022.

On the whole fleet, the global strike frequency is around $1.3 * 10^{-6}$ / F.H.

For the Super Puma family the strike frequency is around $1.6 * 10^{-5}$ / F.H mainly because these helicopters are frequently operating in the North sea region where climatic conditions are favorable to experiment lightning strikes.

ARP5414B/ED-91A indicated that the global strike frequency on rotorcraft is around $1.4 * 10^{-6}$ / F.H.

From 1976 to 2021, at AH, 7 cases of major incidents were noted, plus one accident (AS332MK1 n° 2044, 19 January 1995) among the 126 detected lightning strikes, all due to damage on rotor blades, except one case due to degradation of a main rotor actuator.

All the major incidents were analyzed, in order to confirm the safe return and landing had never been endangered.

Concerning the accident, the AAIB investigations (U.K.) showed that the lightning strike was certainly above the standard severity. The tail blade had been qualified in the early 80's to the standard TSS8.6 (around 1/3 of the action integral of the current waveform A).The consequence was the reinforcement of the design of the tail blades, a qualification up to AC-20-53A and a gradual retrofit of the fleet. Since this event, all the super-puma carbon blades have a protection adapted to match the current lightning standard.

Some margin tests had been done also on some main and tail blades showing that the surface protection installed on blades could resist to action integral of, at least, 1.5 the one of zone 1A (damage only on protection). This rule was adopted after the series of major incidents and the accident in the 90's and the result was naturally a great benefit in terms of safety and customer satisfaction.

The following data are provided for information.

Table 3: Airbus H/Cs Struck by Lightning (from 1976 to 2021)

H/C Type	Number of H/C struck	Number of H/C struck in North Sea
Super Puma	77 (64 MK1 & 10 MK2 & 3 EC225)	59 (47 MK1 & 10 MK2 & 2 EC225)
BO105	1	0
BK117 – EC/H145	5	0
Ecureuil/A-STAR	18	/
Dolphin	11 (1 AS366GA)	2 (AS365)
Puma	9	/
Gazelle	1	/
H120	3	/
NH90	1	/
Total	126	61

Remarks: Data from North Sea are highlighted since about half of the events occurred in this area. 20 H/C were struck on the ground.

Table 4: Items Damaged by Lightning Strike (from 1976 to 2021)

Items		Number
Blades	Main Rotor Blade	227
	Tail Rotor Blade	55
Equipment		45
Structure	Landing Gear	11 (1 in flight)
	Tip of Tail Fin	4
	Horizontal Stabilizer	8
	Dischargers (tail)	2
	Fuselage (bottom part)	1
	Tail Skid	3
Radome		1

Remark: Exposed parts observed through H/Cs struck in service, are in line with exposed parts identified though the typical zoning provided in documents ED-91/ARP-5414.

Rotors and blades in particular, are the items the most frequently damaged, due to their exposure, shape, nature of materials (conductive: metal, carbon).

Damage on the airframe and radome is much less frequent than on rotors. The other damaged areas correspond mainly to protuberances of the rotorcraft, as in rear parts with tip of horizontal stabilizers, tip of tail fin, tail skids

Considering the classification in zone 2A of the main airfoil and root of the blades, even if the phenomenon of sweeping seems natural to be taken into account on rotors (around 4 rev/s for the main and 20 rev./s for the tail), the level of 100 KA is much more severe than what is noted in terms of

damage in service, so the question of a change could be legitimate, either an adaptation of the peak of zone 2A but that needs new characterizations of the threat and changes in standard document (ED-84), or a change of classification of the main airfoil of blades, the possibility being a zone 3N (40 KA); in this last case, the purpose would be to focus on the associated peak level rather than on the mode of interaction (zone 2 deals with sweeping, while zone 3N deals with attachment).

For information in the new documents ARP5414B/ED91A the experience of 3 helicopter manufacturers including AH (letter X) is mentioned.

Table 5: Lightning Strike data from rotorcraft manufacturers in ARP5414B/ED-91A

Rotorcraft Manufacturer	Lightning Strike Reports	Main Rotor Blades	Tail Rotor Blades	Tail Fin	Horizontal Stabilizer	Holst or Cargo Line	Landing Gear	Stinger	Nose	Belly
X	122	106	24	3	8	0	1	3	1*	0
Y	44	29	6	1	5	3	0	2	0	0
Z	52	52	47	1	6	0	0	0	0	1*
Total	218	187	77	5	19	3	1	5	1*	1*

* Old data with just one line referring to light radome damage.
* Rotorcraft with retractable undercarriage and V-shaped lower boat hull.

Manufacturer X (AH) included data (end 2018) taken over approximately 40 years with strike frequency of approximately 1.4×10^{-6} per flight hour, but this depends strongly on helicopter utilization. The data includes 17 strikes that occurred on the ground. The total number of struck blades includes 225 main blades and 54 tail blades. Manufacturer Y had 70 lightning strikes reported between 1981 and 2014, of which 26 were reported as on the ground and so excluded from the table, and 12 for which no damage details are available. Total flight hours are not available. Manufacturer Z had 52 in-flight lightning strikes reported. Strike frequency rates depend on operations.

The majority of reported lightning strike attachments are to the main and tail rotor blades, in many cases attaching to more than one blade. Some strikes have also been reported to the tail fin, horizontal stabilizers and the stinger on the lower trailing surface of the tail boom. The percentage of rotorcraft strikes reported as occurring to the nose is less than 0.5%. The percentage of rotorcraft strikes reported as occurring to the belly is less than 0.5%.

Remark: The data for AH (letter X) are not exactly the same as in table 3 since data in table 3 are more recent and include the last lightning events).

The new zoning is consequently in line with the experience in service.

However, ED-91A/ARP5414B asks to consider the possible modification of the zoning by a local protuberance, in particular if the landing gear is retracted, or due to the presence of local protrusions (antennas, other external equipment items).

3.4 New H/C Zoning, Next steps

The prediction of the effect of a local protrusion, with a better assessment of the risk of attachment would be helpful in order to define the adequate protections and demonstrations. It appears that new methods could be needed to make such assessments, providing reliable criteria to segregate zone 3 with zone 1 and 2. The ARP5414-B/ED-91A document has a specific chapter (§ 8.3) to introduce the modeling of zoning as a possible approach, but this method needs complementary investigations, and a validation process. Such a reliable prediction tool would be beneficial, in addition to the effect of protrusions, as emphasized by ARP5414B/ED-91A § 9.1. In addition, the aim would be to establish zoning for new unconventional aircraft (e.g. VTOL as City Airbus in the frame of Urban mobility, High-speed rotorcraft like Racer, ...) for which by nature no experience exists to define a zoning.

Other applications could be the treatment of drones for which, in agreement with the authorities/customers, the aggression scenario could be relaxed to save weight and costs, and for instance by a focus on the main areas submitted to the highest risks of attachments.

Figure 6: Racer

Figure 7: City Airbus

As an example of numerical simulation the next following part will present the results obtained on a complete Helicopter with the Airbus electromagnetic numerical tool for primary attachment locations prediction, the limitations of such a prediction tool and the recommendations in terms of utilization of the tool and associated protection policy.

4. NUMERICAL SIMULATION OF PRIMARY ATTACHMENT AREAS ON H175 ROTORCRAFT

4.1 Context and objectives

In the context of the new zoning definition of helicopters, it is necessary to evaluate if all protuberances located around the nose and below (optional equipment in some cases) can be considered as small protrusions as per ARP5414B/ED-91A (§ 9.1) and if a direct attachment is likely with the same level of

risk than the areas considered today in zone 1. A classification of the helicopter nose in lightning zone 3 would not only influence the lightning direct effect protection to be implemented in this area, but also the lightning strikes scenario to be considered for the lightning indirect effect compliance process. Indeed, the removal of a nose to tail parts lightning strike scenario alleviates the lightning protection effort on some electrical systems installed in front of the H/C fuselage (i.e. harness overshielding, equipment lightning internal protection).

According to the in-flight experience reported previously, there is rather no event involving the nose. In order to confirm this statistical observation, a simulation approach has been considered to verify if the classification of the nose as a zone 3 is unconditional, by evaluating the sensitivity of the attachment areas with the presence of various flight configurations and presence of various optional equipment units which can be mounted on the nose.

The main purpose of the simulation approach was first to assess whether the simulation results are consistent with the in-service observation, i.e. low attachment risk on the nose and radome strips. Finally an analysis has been done on the impact of various protruding equipment (FLIR camera, Tactical radar, Pitot probes, VHF antenna) but also a fuel probe, on the nose area attachment risks.

4.2 Numerical methodology

In the frame of the A400M aircraft program, a theoretical assessment of the attachment probabilities has been done using a numerical methodology based on the positive leader inception model and developed in the frame of the ASERIS suite of software. The numerical model, its applicability, limitations and key parameters have been described [8] and will be then just summarized in this paper.

A lightning attachment is likely to occur at a location on the aircraft when conditions for having a leader propagation are fulfilled, corresponding by hypothesis to reaching the streamer-leader transition.

Using an electrical approach, this transition is supposed to be achieved at a point P on the aircraft surface while verifying the two criterions:

- On the electric field ($E_P > E_{\text{threshold}} \equiv$ breakdown field in air, so 30 KV/cm at sea level)
- On the electrical charge Q_{Stab} available inside a small volume around P (called stability or corona volume) to feed this transition process ($Q > Q_{\text{crit}} \sim$ few μC , up to 5 μC)

The modeling principle to determine attachment areas is based on the following sequence:

- Likely conditions to a lightning strike triggered by an aircraft is modeled by an ambient field in every direction $E_A(\theta, \phi)$, with a typical angular sweeping step of 10° , so it is considered an equiprobability of the ambient field directions
- Poisson equation is solved to determine the surface charge density on the object ($\sigma_P \equiv$ normal electric field at any point P)

- Locations where the streamer-leader transition is likely to be reached in first are obtained by verifying the previous criterions:
 - We determine the location $P_0(\theta, \phi)$ where the E field exceeds in first the breakdown threshold E_{Th}
 - We compute the charge Q_{Stab} contained within the area around $P_0(\theta, \phi)$ and delimited by the iso field boundary $E = E_{Stab}$ (stability field $\sim 5kV/cm$)
- Attachment probabilities density are finally derived from a weighted counting of the number of occurrences at each location P and its associated stability area

Figure 8: Primary attachment locations evaluation methodology. (a): static field simulating the static stress prior to attachment ; (b): stability volume around first air breakdown location ; (c): Primary attachment probability density classified in different probabilities areas (High, Low, Null) [8]

4.3 H175 Numerical model

The meshing of the H175 helicopter has been done according to electrostatic constraints and specific zoning analysis requirements [8]. For instance, it is necessary to harmonize the level of meshing refinement over all protrusions (blades, strips, cable breakers, gears/axles, probes and VHF ...). Some parts have been adapted to fulfill those requirements (nose strips, VHF). Pure dielectric helicopter surfaces and parts have been removed while low conductive ones have been considered as perfectly conductive, regarding the quasi static approach followed for simulating prior attachment conditions (the helicopter is moving nearby lightning cells before triggering streamer-leader transition on the airframe). In that configuration, main blades are oriented at 36° with regards to the helicopter axis (x direction), fuel probe is not present, front and main landing gears are deployed (respectively FLG and MLG) but pneumatics are not represented (supposed to be too resistive to play a role). The orientation of the blades (36°) has been considered for the reference case as it corresponds to the worst case in terms of protection lack of the nose, the objective being also to evaluate the likeliness of an attachment on the nose.

Figure 9: Meshed model of H175 helicopter for zoning analysis purpose

Figure 10a&b: Details of the model. (a) VHF antenna & FLIR; (b): Landing gear (pneumatics removed)

In order to ease the identification of the main attachment areas and their relative importance, the H175 has been divided into sub-domains where specific attention will be made.

Figure 11: Sub-domains of H175 helicopter - upper part

Figure 12: Sub-domains of H175 helicopter - lower part

4.4 Analysis of the reference case

We present first the mapping of the primary attachment locations obtained for the reference case (REF).

Figure 13: Attachment probability density for the reference H175 case configuration (REF). ■ Likely to be a primary attachment area with high probability; ■ Likely to be a primary attachment area with low probability; ■ Unlikely to be a primary attachment area

In that reference configuration, 6 locations have been identified as probable primary attachment areas. Let's introduce the attachment probability for a given area i as the summation over all directions (θ, ϕ) of the number of weighted cases that have induced an attachment on that area, normalized to the total number of directions considered in the simulations, N_T :

$$P_i = 100 \frac{\sum_{\theta=0}^{\theta=180} \sum_{\phi=0}^{\phi=350} P_i(\theta, \phi)}{N_\tau}$$

Where $P_i(\theta, \phi) = w$ if the area i is the primary attachment for (θ, ϕ) and 0 if not, where w is a weight that depends on the local field amplitude and, possibly, on (θ, ϕ) . For the reference case, it leads to following attachment repartition:

Table 6: Attachment repartition versus H175 areas for the reference configuration. Other Helicopter areas not reported in that table are not attachment areas and have significantly larger margins ($R_{min} > 5-10$)

Case	Attachment repartition (%)					
	Main blades	Tail blades	Stabilizer	FLG	MLG	Radome strips
REF	45.9	29.3	14.8	3.6	5.6	0.8

From a qualitative point of view, compared to the experience in service (Table 5), the global attachment repartition is correct in the sense that the 3 main attachment areas (main and tail blades, and stabilizer) are well predicted as those gathering about 90% of the events.

Quantitatively, that attachment repartition between these 3 main areas differs from in-service experience. This can be due first to the meshed model refinement, then on hypotheses on the prior helicopter electrostatic net charging state, on the way attachment probabilities are weighted versus ambient field amplitude and directions but also on the local electric field in the stability area, and finally on the difference between real lightning conditions (position of the helicopter with regards to the lightning cell) compared to those modeled by iso probable directions of the ambient field. It is highly probable that this latter difference could lead to different attachment repartition between the 3 main ones, while not modifying the very low attachment probability on other areas.

We report in the next table all other locations not found to be primary attachment but highlighting the "protection" margin for this area. For each area, 2 information are reported: R_{min} and protection area:

- Line 1:

$$R_{min} = \min_{\theta, \phi} \left\{ \frac{E_{max} \text{ of the area identified as the attachment location}}{E_{max} \text{ of the "protected" area}} \right\}$$

- Line 2: the area found as the attachment location for (θ, ϕ) leading to R_{min}

Table 7: Protection margin for areas not found as primary attachment areas. Other Helicopter areas not reported in that table have significantly larger margins ($R_{min} > 5-10$)

Case	Min protection margin for other locations					
	Tactical ant. strips	FLIR	VHF	Cable breaker	Deflectors	Pitots
REF	1.5	3.6	1.7	2.5	2.6	2.5
	Radome strips	MLG	MLG	Main blades	Radome strips	Radome strips

It is important to understand that what is reported in the previous table corresponds to the closest conditions for which an attachment on these zones is likely to occur, the protection

margin of these zones being equal or greater than that. This protection margin is rather small, for instance for the tactical antenna that has a margin of 1.5 only, just less exposed to an attachment than the radome. As a consequence, some caution should be taken, considering however that if the risk to be an attachment location remains, the probability is rather low as it is similar to that of the radome strips that have been reported from in-service to be globally not an attachment area.

4.5 Sensitivity analysis with flight and equipment configurations

In order to evaluate the relevance of the previous primary attachment areas identification, we have performed a sensitivity analysis in two directions:

- H175 model representativeness: presence of pneumatics, representation of the windshield, model of radome strips, refinement of angular sweeping
- H175 flight configuration: fuel probe, landing gears deployed or not, presence of antennas, main blades position

We report in the table below some of the configurations evaluated in that study (one reference case and 9 alternative configurations) for which results will be presented in this paper.

Table 8: Configurations evaluated by numerical simulation. Modifications versus reference case are highlighted in blue

Case	Configuration					
	Fuel probe	Land. gears	Pneumatics	Main blades	FLIR	Tactical ant.
REF	Absent	Deployed	Absents	36°	Present	Present
M1	Absent	Deployed	Presents	36°	Present	Present
M2	Absent	Retracted	Absents	36°	Present	Present
M3	Absent	Retracted	Absents	36°	Absent	Absent
M4	Absent	Deployed	Absents	36°	Absent	Absent
M5	Absent	Deployed	Absents	0°	Present	Present
M6	Present	Deployed	Absents	36°	Present	Present
M7	Present	Deployed	Absents	0°	Present	Present
M8	Present	Retracted	Absents	0°	Present	Present
M9	Absent	Retracted	Absents	0°	Present	Present

Retracted landing gears and fuel probe configurations are shown on the next figures:

Figure 14: H175 helicopter in retracted gears configuration (main landing gears are still protruding from the airframe)

Figure 15: H175 helicopter configuration with the refueling probe

Remark: Configuration with fuel probe is a virtual configuration, for the purpose of this paper, but it does not exist.

The attachment repartitions obtained for all these configurations are reported in the next table.

Table 9: Attachment repartition versus H175 areas for all the configurations evaluated. Other Helicopter areas not reported in that table are not attachment areas and have significantly larger margins ($R_{min} > 5-10$)

Case	Attachment repartition (%)							
	Main blades	Tail blades	Stab.	Fuel probe	FLG	MLG	Radome strips	Tactical ant. strips
REF	45.9	29.3	14.8	Absent	3.6	5.6	0.8	0
M1	46.4	29.3	18.3	Absent	0	0	5.7	0.3
M2	46.3	29.3	16.9	Absent	0	4.1	3.4	0
M3	46.1	29.3	16.9	Absent	0	3.8	3.9	0
M4	45.8	29.3	14.8	Absent	4.4	4.7	1	0
M5	44.4	30.8	15.5	Absent	4.1	4.9	0.3	0
M6	44.3	29.3	14.8	3.8	1.6	6.2	0	0
M7	42.2	30.8	15.8	3.9	1.5	5.8	0	0
M8	42.7	30.6	17.4	6.5	0	2.8	0	0
M9	44.6	30.8	17.3	Absent	0	3.9	3.4	0

These results first confirm the weak probability of attachment on the radome strips or on any protrusions close to the nose (FLIR, VHF, cable breakers and deflectors, pitot probes). Attachment on blades and stabilizer corresponds to about 90% of the attachments found. Landing gears are likely to be primary attachment locations in 3 to 10% depending on the configuration, radome strips being an attachment location for 3-4% of the whole. Note that events involving radome strips and protrusions nearby are associated with lightning scenarios where the tail blades are always the exit point.

The comparison between REF and M1 cases shows that the presence of pneumatics tends first to reduce to zero the risk of attachment on the landing gears but more interesting, it reinforces the attachment probability on radome strips and leads to a few attachment on the tactical antenna strips. However, the presence of pneumatics appeared to be an improper way to represent the real behavior of that area and thus have been removed for the rest of the study.

Landing gears are likely to be struck with a low probability (higher for the main landing gear). When gears are not deployed, there is a residual risk of attachment on the main landing gears as, even in retracted configuration, they are still protruding from the airframe (what is not the case for the nose landing gear).

As highlighted by configurations M6 to M8, the fuel probe is likely to be struck but with a low probability as it is mostly protected by the main blades, whatever their position (0 or 36° configuration).

As shown in the next table, in many cases, the margin of protection for areas not detected as attachment areas is moderate or weak (radar strips and VHF). It means that any modification of the design could impact the result of the model and lead to those zones to become primary attachment areas. However, this will be associated with a low probability (rare event).

Table 10: Protection margin for areas not found as primary attachment locations over all simulated configurations

Min protection margin for other locations over all orientations and helicopter configurations					
Protected area	FLIR	VHF	Cable breaker	Deflectors	Pitots
Rmin	2.5	1.15	2.2	2	2.2
Protected by	Radar strips	Stabilizer	Main blades	Stabilizer	Radome strips

5. CONCLUSION

Attachment locations predicted by the numerical method on H175 H/C have shown results with a global qualitative agreement with the experience in service. These predictions allow discriminating risk levels between the large protrusions as the rotor blades and the rear part of the helicopter (stabilizer and tail fin) with most of the other parts of the airframe, either flush or with small protrusions.

Concerning the quantitative differences on the predicted repartitions, it should be kept in mind that:

- Experimental figures strongly depend on in-service experience from a manufacturer to another and from a rotorcraft model to another
- They are based on damage observation locations that could include subsequent return strikes after some sweeping period
- The modeling is based on assumptions on lightning conditions simulation, for instance the hypothesis of equiprobabilities of ambient field orientations.

Improving the numerical methodology to better reproduce in-service observations could be relevant as the numerical tool is considered to be a critical means to take decisions, and quantitative repartitions are not fully satisfactory. For instance, it could be relevant to evaluate the impact of the net electrostatic state of the helicopter due to triboelectric charging on the attachment locations repartition. In addition, as explained previously, the model of ambient field orientations could be adapted with more representative configurations, considering that helicopters experience a lightning strike mostly at very low altitude, meaning nearly vertical E fields (with a certain angle) and see if such an assumption has a significant effect or not.

In the present situation, if there is no doubt about the classification of blades tips in a zone 1A, for the airframe parts and in particular the protrusions, it is more difficult to classify either in a zone 1B or in a pure zone 3 (more or less assimilated to a conduction zone).

The modeling results are also reaffirming the pertinence of the evolution of the generic H/C zoning in the last issue of the ARP5414/ED 91 guide, especially the classification of the nose as a zone 3. The low likelihood identified by both the simulation and the experience for an attachment on the nose is explained by the protection brought by the main blades so that the propensity to attach in this area remains low even with the presence of significant protrusions installed in the nose area.

That is why, in case of doubts, a reasonable compromise could be a classification in a zone 3N, as indicated above, while the more conventional zone 1B should be preferred for the biggest protrusions escaping from the protection of rotors and/or in particular if the consequences of damage are potentially catastrophic.

In other words, the classification in zone 1B can also be

relevant when the consequences of the attachment on this protrusion might lead to a catastrophic situation.

Finally, it should be kept in mind that the model does not predict the zoning of the aircraft but, within the scope of these defined limitations, it does provide leader attachment relative probabilities, and that contributes to the definition of the zoning.

It can be reminded that a typical utilization could be as done for the A400M, so to analyze a delta-zoning, by adding an external element (as a fuel probe) and to check the effect on a well-known reference (the classical zoning of the nose of the aircraft).

6. REFERENCES

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